

Utilizing the Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale in the Third Trimester to Decrease Postpartum Depression

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Background

- Postpartum depression (PPD) can affect up to 20% of new mothers
- PPD may result in significant adverse effects to mother and child
- If left untreated, PPD may escalate to psychosis
- Up to 40% of those with PPD will relapse in future pregnancies
- Early detection leads to early treatment, early management, and better health outcomes

Problem

- Perinatal depression is under-screened and underreported
- There are no consistent screening practices
- Women may not seek treatment due to lack of education, stigma, or shame
- 50%-60% of women do not attend their postpartum visit

Purpose

- Screen early for depression
- Identify risk before delivery
- Refer to treatment if indicated
- Promote maternal mental health wellness
- Decrease incidence of postpartum depression

The Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice Framework

Discussion

- Three-month pilot project did not show statistically significant results
- Outcomes were clinically significant as all participants' postpartum EPDS total scores were <10
- Early routine assessment for depression provides opportunity to validate the patient's fears and concerns, and offer support

Limitations

- Limited time resulted in small sample size
- Some participants did not attend the postpartum visit
- Patient questionnaire may be mislabeled or lost
- Narrow demographics could compromise generalizability

Recommendations

- Further research with larger, more diverse population for conclusive results
- Evidence supporting importance of early depression screening will influence recommendations to promote organizational change in favor of screening for depression in the third trimester of pregnancy

References

References upon request
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Results

Independent Sample t-test
Mean Postpartum EPDS total scores between baseline group and intervention group $t(45) = .953, p = .346$

Paired Sample t-test

- Mean EPDS total scores between baseline initial visit and postpartum $t(32) = 1.09, p = .282$
- Mean EPDS total scores between intervention initial visit and postpartum $t(12) = 1.908, p = .081$
- Mean EPDS total scores between intervention third trimester and postpartum $t(12) = 1.73, p = .109$